

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of analyzing the interaction between the Asia-Pacific countries is due to several key factors, in particular, the fact that it is one of the most dynamically developing in the world. Countries such as China, India, and Southeast Asia demonstrate high economic growth rates, which affects global financial processes. The topic is essential because this region is becoming an arena for geopolitical competition, especially between major powers such as the US and China. This affects international relations and security in the area. APAC is an important global trade and investment center, making its transformation significant for the world economy.

Thus, enhancing economic growth and strengthening the APAC community, as well as studying the interaction of the economies of APAC under the AUKUS alliance, is essential for understanding contemporary global processes and their impact on the future.

Literature Review

The Indo-Pacific region remains a defining area in the new era of discord between China and the US, signifying a looming struggle for global and regional primacy and competing positions between the two states. The U.S. National Security Strategy 2022 notes that in addition to Moscow's "imperialist foreign policy," Beijing's attempt to "reshape the international order" forces Washington to intensify and deepen its network of alliances in the Indo-Pacific. Among the most notable of these alliances is AUKUS, an essential and evolving security pact [1]. The further likely expansion of this alliance is generating considerable debate about how it could potentially affect the changing dynamics of the highly uncertain security environment in APAC.

We have highlighted several publications that help further understand the specifics of the interaction of APAC economies in the context of the AUKUS alliance.

According to R. U. Zaman and L. Yasmin, the functionality of this kind of alliance can be questioned. Several associations have been formed and exist, but they do not have any clear goals and objectives. The authors argue that AUKUS would be one such alliance that started with numerous promises, but its fundamental proposal to counter China's rise in the Indo-Pacific is impractical [2].

It is also necessary to pay attention to the economic differences in the level of APAC countries, particularly the large gap between the developed and developing countries. For example, Japan, South Korea, and Australia have rapidly growing economies with high living standards and modern technology. At the same time, countries such as Laos and Cambodia face serious economic challenges and poverty.

B. Tan et al. compare the APAC countries in terms of the level of “knowledge economy,” i.e., the highest stage of development of a post-industrial, innovative economy characterized by the information society. According to the authors, four countries (India, Indonesia, Thailand, and mainland China) are considered inefficient in development compared to the other eight. The main reason for their lagging behind is the outflow of their human capital to other developed countries [3].

Thai-Ha Le and Binh Tran-Nam studied the relationship between trade liberalization, financial modernization, and economic development in 14 APAC countries in 1961-2011. The authors divided the 14 countries studied into two subsamples: high-income countries and middle-income countries. The results obtained by the authors indicate unidirectional causal relationships: from financial modernization to economic development, trade liberalization to economic development, and trade liberalization to financial modernization [4].

M. S. Nasir et al. studied the impact of corruption, foreign investment, population growth, and government spending on economic development in 10 APAC countries. They found that bribery does not significantly affect economic growth, while foreign investment, population growth, and government spending substantially impact economic growth [5].

Notably, dependence of APAC countries on the US is multifaceted and affects the economy, security, geopolitical realities, and culture. Economically, the US is one of the largest trading partners for many APAC countries; for instance, Japan and South Korea export their products to the US. The US is vital in financing and investment, contributing to the region's economic growth.

Frank S.T Hsiao et al. confirm the relationship between the U.S. and APAC countries, and this relationship is found through analyzing trade, investment, and stock market data. According to the authors, there is no unidirectional relationship between the GDP of these countries. Still, the decline of US stock price indices can cause a recession in Japan, Korea, and Taiwan [6].

W. Zhang et al. find that in the short term, the 2007 U.S. credit crisis has put intense pressure on the APAC economies through financial linkages and the traditional trade channel due to the deepening of global economic integration. The relative importance of different financial channels varies markedly across economies [7].

A number of works dedicated to the development of APAC countries within the framework of such initiatives as BRICS, Trans-Pacific Partnership and Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership are also highlighted.

According to N. Haibin, BRICS group does not pay enough attention to Asian economic or security issues in East Asia. The priority of BRICS countries is to promote their global status, which makes regional issues less attractive. The author believes that Asia is not a highly integrated region, partly because of competition among major powers, including the Asian members of BRICS [8].

I. Cheong and J. Tongzon analyze such economic integrations as the Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) and the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP), evaluate their economic effects, and predict the consequences in East Asia using quantitative methods [9].

According to K. Kawasaki, TPP and RCEP are not competitors but complementary agreements, as both are key elements for forming the Asia-Pacific Free Trade Area. The author believes the roles of the U.S. in the TPP and China in the RCEP are auspicious in terms of creating economic benefits and geopolitical reasons [10].

E. Andal analyzes the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)'s impact on economic integration in APAC. The analysis of trade flows leads the author to conclude that its intensity occurs. Still, on average, ASEAN does not retain a central role in developing APAC [11].

ASEAN expressed concerns about AUKUS, possible negative consequences for regional stability, and their strategic approaches to relations with the United States and China.

M. Li notes that AUKUS could trigger a regional arms race in certain areas on a limited scale and cause more problems for regional stability. According to the author, AUKUS may provide a flexible new way of strategic realignment in the Indo-Pacific region. Against the backdrop of the growing strategic rivalry between the US and China, the strategic landscape in the Indo-Pacific may become even more fragmented and competitive [12].

Thus, the problem of interaction between the APAC economies under the AUKUS alliance includes several key aspects; in particular, several questions arise: how does the creation of blocs such as AUKUS affect the balance of power in the region? Can it lead to changes in security strategies and alliances? How do the blocs affect economic relations between the area's countries regarding trade, investment, and technological cooperation? How do other states, such as China and Russia, react to the creation of such blocs?

The purpose of the article is to explore these aspects which may help understand the possibilities of interaction between the APAC economies under the AUKUS alliance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Publications in peer-reviewed journals in economics, international relations, security, and politics were used to study the interaction of APAC economies under the alliance. In particular, the following publications were used: "The Journal of Asian Economics," "Journal of Modelling in Management," "International Organizations Research Journal," "Asian Economic Papers," "Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy," "China International Strategy Review," as well as articles from authoritative news publications analyzing events and trends in international politics, such as "The Economist" and "The Washington Times."

Research methods: analysis of official documents related to NATO, AUKUS, and RCEP, as well as reports of other international organizations; comparative study of AUKUS with other blocs and alliances to assess differences and similarities in approaches to security.

RESULTS

Contemporary international relations in APAC are not only a complex system integrated into the foreign policy of interests confrontation between the East and West countries, preserving the features of the bipolar era but are also a direct projection of global processes. Transformation of a vast and densely populated region, with unresolved problems of both local and international character, is caused by the intensive development of technology in the XXI century, which determines the list of new priority problems of the region. The key role is played by economic and security issues such as:

- Interstate conflicts and territorial disputes;
- Militarization of the region;
- Increased number of nuclear weapons in the region;
- Digitalization of processes and, consequently, emergence of cyber threats;
- Socio-economic problems:
- Crisis of forced migration of the population;
- Lack of quality primary and secondary education (SEA);
- Poverty and financial stratification of society;
- A large number of stateless persons;
- Surplus of untapped labor resources.

APAC is a vast and dynamic historical and cultural area of interest to regional states and external actors [13]. Southeast Asia's rapidly growing and active able-bodied population, availability of all vital resources, developed industrial and scientific-technical complex, and favorable environment for investment determine the intensive economic growth. According to expert estimates, the region accounts for 30% to 40% of world production.

In the post-bipolar era, there is a new need to expand the boundaries of APAC and transform it into the Indo-Pacific region. The main reason cited by Western political scientists is the initiative to limit and reduce the influence of countries that represent economies independent of the US and to provoke further friction between them. If the name APAC contains 'Asia', The Indo-Pacific intentionally does not convey belonging to a part of the world and, therefore, its cultural heritage, limiting itself to the name of the waters of the oceans (Indo-Pacific) [14].

The most likely scenario for the further evolution of APAC is the subsequent introduction of new bloc initiatives, which, according to the West, will lead to the weakening of the “axis of evil” [15] (Russia, China, North Korea) – the eastern reincarnation of the “Evil Empire,” as well as the complete Westernization of the region on the example of the quadripartite security dialogue QUAD, and the same bloc AUKUS, which, in essence, is analog; it projects NATO's interests in the countries of the Pacific Ocean basin. These formations emerged to counter regional threats and respond to China's economic and political strengthening. While the SCO's activities are aimed primarily at interaction with the countries of Central Asia and the Middle East, the West's monopoly is being consolidated on the countries of Asia. At the same time, the possibility of restoring dialog through the communist regimes of the PRC, DPRK, Vietnam, and Laos with parties in other states of the region looks very promising.

President of the People's Republic of China, Xi Jinping, has repeatedly stated the need to oppose bloc thinking, as such a policy causes world polarization and inevitably leads to the beginning of a new Cold War. The return of the former division into ‘red’ and ‘blue’ becomes an extraordinary challenge due to the growing threat of proliferation of weapons of mass destruction to be deployed in Australia within the framework of the AUKUS defense bloc project.

As X. Shi notes, the AUKUS agreement is the first to authorize a non-nuclear-armed country to have nuclear submarines. It brings the Australia-UK-US alliance into a closer military, scientific, and industrial community and outlines the prototype for a new “maritime alliance.” The coalition seeks to create a “desinonized” defense industrial chain and has thus become a precursor to the restructuring of international relations. The “integrated deterrence” strategy that the alliance is building influences the strategic deterrence structure in the Indo-Pacific region and some essential features of the deterrence strategy of the US alliance system against China [16].

Remarkably, at the moment, there are no precise and unambiguous parallels between organizations that address regional security issues and defensive alliances of the bipolar world.

Construction of a new economic order in the countries of the modern Silk Road is becoming a determining factor in forming an anti-Western financial space, attracting investment, and spreading the Celestial Empire's soft power.

China is trying to expand its borders and gain complete control over the South China Sea, possibly making it its transit zone for maritime trade of APAC countries and allowing it to settle differences in the military sphere. With the help of dredgers – unique construction vessels that lift silt and sand from the seabed – not only islands were created but also dredges and harbors necessary for laying the fairway for large ships. Construction in the South China Sea is of grave concern to Taiwan, Malaysia, the Philippines, and the Anglo-Saxon troika

represented by AUKUS, mainly because Australia's trade with Japan and the Republic of Korea passes through the South China Sea. In this regard, in 2016, Australia stated its desire to more closely scrutinize the UN for China's compliance with the Law of the Sea Convention about claims of sovereignty over the new islands. Australia has formally declared China a threat to national interests. On July 12 of the same year, the Hague Court ruled that the construction of the islands was illegal.

In this regard, it is worth considering the possibility of Japan joining the trilateral alliance AUKUS, which is already an observer and advises the alliance members on cybersecurity issues. The question of expanding the Anglo-Saxon organization and admitting Tokyo, Seoul, Taipei, and Jakarta into its ranks remains open, based on the targeting of the priorities of the leading members. For instance, enlargement would serve as a more substantial barrier against China but could provoke a backlash. Moreover, the key factor of cooperation in resolving military challenges in the region is the speed of decisions, which is the strength of small alliances. Thus, in a confrontation between AUKUS and China, Japan will act as a backstop, focusing on the Middle Kingdom, as it already has long-range missiles capable of reaching China. Another argument is the factor of using nuclear submarines, which will allow Anglo-Saxon countries to remain technological leaders amid their allies, acting as the only competitive force. The other two options are possible solutions initiated by the U.S., implemented with the help and on behalf of its allies. In addition, the possibility of new AUKUS-based entities, e.g., focused on technology partnerships, cannot be ruled out.

DISCUSSION

Regarding Russia's interests in the region, the line of cooperation with ASEAN countries remains, as well as the expansion of blocs such as the SCO, BRICS, and EAEU and the promotion of China's initiatives such as the Belt and Road project. Avoiding polarization and preserving stability in APAC in a polycentric world is becoming a primary task. One cannot but agree with N. K. Mohapatra, according to whom Russia, geographically and geopolitically, through its doctrines of "Greater Eurasia" and "Asian Pivot," is interested in playing an essential role in the Indo-Pacific region. However, the growing role of the United States and the marked increase in China's expansionist policies in the Indo-Pacific also raise concerns for Russia [17].

B. S. Sergi et al. believe that the preferred choice for APAC is cooperation with Russia, which is ready to increase imports of industrial and high-tech products and engage in joint industrial innovation entrepreneurship. Investments will lead to synergistic effects, providing simultaneous industrial, technological, and financial development [18].

The main idea of developing block and allied trends within APAC will increasingly reflect the desire of the United States and China to become unconditional leaders and reference points for countries in the Pacific and Indian oceans in their desire to control and determine their geo-economic and military-technical development, to involve them in monetary integration, to allow them to remain original and thriving within the framework of paternalistic policies of the West and the East, in the conditions of the world sliding towards increasingly likely regional and global conflicts.

The ability to be embedded both in the QUAD, in the RCEP, and especially in the AUKUS gives each country, as a creator of the process, its right to apply the unique knowledge gained at its discretion and to believe in its exclusivity even in the face of seeming external intransigence in the confrontation between the main participants of future conflicts, the U.S. and China, which are engaged in both pacification of the states of the region, and new stitching of the unity of emerging interests. Decoupling, as a process of the yet-to-be-accomplished technological unity of both the US and China, showed there will be no total division of technologies; it is only possible to divide the markets themselves, NBIC technologies, and zones of potential influence and access to the goods and services of an adversary or partner in their transitions from unique original models to a set of substitutes already pulled out by industrial espionage into the “gray markets” of the shadow global economy.

CONCLUSION

The alliance can change regional trade flows by deepening economic ties between members and possibly creating barriers for countries they consider competitors (e.g., China). In response to AUKUS, China may strengthen its financial and military ties with regional neighbors such as Russia and Southeast Asia. This, in turn, will lead to economic competition, which may affect the cost of resources and goods. The effect of AUKUS on the region's economy could lead to stronger integration between partner countries and more intense competition for trade routes and resources. Thus, the AUKUS alliance significantly affects the economic interaction of Asia-Pacific countries, creating new opportunities and causing potential threats for both alliance members and independent countries in the region.

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